

Continuing the Chronicle of Caribbean Mantodea: Distributional Expansions and Taxonomic Revisions

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Abstract. Consolidation of recent taxonomic revisions, nomenclatural corrections, and newly documented distribution records for the Caribbean Mantodea. Fifty-two (52) new island records extend known species ranges and include many first records for previously unsampled islands. Updated species accounts, diagnostic keys, and remarks discuss the status of adventive and endemic taxa.

Anderson's *Praying Mantises of the Caribbean* (2021) text presented a comprehensive taxonomic treatment of all known species of Mantodea occurring within the Caribbean region. That work included a full review and presentation of species-level taxonomy, the description of one new species, the revision of status for two others, and detailed accounts of natural history and distribution for each taxon. The present supplement serves to update that foundational work by documenting the taxonomic changes and distributional records that have emerged since its publication. Notably, several generic revisions have affected the placement of Caribbean taxa, necessitating updated combinations and nomenclatural adjustments. In addition, a growing number of photographic observations that have been submitted through the iNaturalist.org platform have yielded fifty-two (52) new island records, extending known ranges for numerous species. This supplement aggregates all newly available data, provides photographic documentation of relevant taxa, and includes an updated dichotomous key to the Mantodea of the Caribbean.

While reviewing the new island records, it is critical to understand that the documented chronology of these observations may not reflect the actual timeline of species dispersal. The fact that these new island populations were most recently discovered does not necessarily mean that they are newly established. On the contrary, these may represent some of the oldest and most stable colonies of the relevant taxa of the region, previously undocumented due to a lack of historical entomological surveys. The growing accessibility of high-resolution phone cameras and the proliferation in use of the iNaturalist.org platform have increased both the frequency and quality of faunal documentation by the general public, revealing species presence that have long existed unnoticed. It is also plausible, however, that these new island records do reflect recent colonization events, potentially facilitated by modern human activity such as inter-island trade, travel, and cargo movement. Whether ancient or recent, these new records underscore the remarkable dispersal capability and adaptability of the species treated herein, while also emphasizing the importance of ongoing citizen science in mapping the true range of Caribbean Mantodea. Overall, these findings highlight the broader issue of underdocumentation of Mantodea across the Caribbean, where many islands, especially the smaller or uninhabited ones, remain biologically unexplored. It is

highly probable that other islands within the Caribbean host undescribed or unrecorded Mantodea taxa, and future surveys or citizen-science contributions may continue to expand both species counts and distribution ranges in the region. As such, these new records continue to reshape our understanding of Caribbean Mantodea distribution and reinforce the value of community science as a tool for uncovering long-neglected corners of biodiversity.

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Key to the Mantodea Genera of the Caribbean:

- 1 Cerci conical or cylindrical throughout, occasionally with flattened terminal segment 2
- 1' Cerci compressed, broadly foliaceous throughout *Angela*

- 2 Pronotum without having lateral margins expanded 3
- 2' Pronotum with lateral margins expanded *Epaphrodita*

- 3 Pronotum elongate, spanning much narrower than length; metazona measures longer than prozona 4
- 3' Pronotum quadrangular, spanning as wide as long; metazona measures nearly as long as prozona *Mantoida*

- 4 Costal margin of male forewings unarmed or with few bristles. Females macropterous or brachypterous 5
- 4' Costal margin of male forewings armed with numerous diminutive bristles. Females apterous . 11

- 5 Forefemora armed with 5 posteroventral spines 6
- 5' Forefemora armed with 4 posteroventral spines 10

- 6 Compound eyes rounded, globulous, sometimes conical but not acute. Habitus resembles live vegetation; general coloration typically greenish 7
- 6' Compound eyes ovoid with an apical conical point. Habitus resembles dead, desiccated leaves; general coloration brownish, never green *Acanthops*

- 7 Pronotum slender, elongated, metazona carinate. Body length measures ≥ 30 mm. Male subgenital plate with styli 8
- 7' Pronotum stout, rather short and stocky, smooth throughout. Body length measures < 30 mm. Male subgenital plate without styli 9

- 8 Pronotum with smooth lateral margins. Antennae entirely filiform. Females macropterous *Paraphotina*
- 8' Pronotum with lateral margins denticulate to strongly toothed. Base of antennae conspicuously thickened. Females brachypterous *Brunneria*

- 9 Posteroventral spines of foretibiae straight, spaced apart, oblique. Supracoxal dilation slightly marked or inconspicuous. Metazona broad in middle, lateral margins subparallel. Lower frons 4 to 5 times wider than high *Tithrone*
- 9' Posteroventral spines of foretibiae curved, close together, recumbent. Supracoxal dilation well defined. Metazona compressed in middle, lateral margins sinuate. Lower frons 2 to 3 times wider than high *Acontista*

- 10 Habitus dorsoventrally flattened. Occurs on tree trunks, strictly bark-dwelling 25
- 10' Habitus more proportionate, not flattened. Occurs in a variety of vegetation habitats 17

11	Forefemora armed with 11-15 anteroventral spines. Foretibiae without dorsal spines	14
11'	Forefemora armed with no more than 10 anteroventral spines. Foretibiae with or without dorsal spines	12
12	Foretibiae with dorsal spines	13
12'	Foretibiae without dorsal spines	15
13	Head capsule armed with postocellar process. Foretibiae armed with 4-5 anteroventral spines	<i>Thesprotiella</i>
13'	Head capsule unarmed. Foretibiae without anteroventral spines	<i>Thesprotia</i>
14	Metazona measures as long as forecoxae. Lower frons measures 4 times wider than tall. Anteroventral spines of foretibiae forming two groups, each group of spines gradually increasing in size distad	<i>Musonia</i>
14'	Metazona measures longer than forecoxae. Lower frons measures 5-6 times wider than tall. Anteroventral spines of foretibiae forming one consistent group, all spines confluent increasing in size distad	<i>Paramusonia</i>
15	Foretibiae armed with 1-2 posteroventral spines	16
15'	Foretibiae armed with 7 posteroventral spines	<i>Bantiella</i>
16	Foretibiae armed with 2 posteroventral and 3 anteroventral spines. Juxtaocular bulges rounded, not produced	<i>Liguanea</i>
16'	Foretibiae armed with 1 posteroventral and 3-6 anteroventral spines. Juxtaocular bulges prominent, strongly conical	<i>Oligonyx</i>
17	Head capsule bearing pair of distinct ocellar processes	18
17'	Head capsule without ocellar process	19
18	Metathoracic legs lobed. Male antennae pectinate	<i>Vates</i>
18'	Metathoracic legs simple. Male antennae serrate	<i>Pseudovates</i>
19	Compound eyes rounded or conical. Discoidal area of male forewings largely or entirely immaculate throughout. Female forewings reaching to or slightly surpassing tip of abdomen ..	20
19'	Compound eyes rounded. Discoidal area of male forewings infumate or mottled throughout. Female forewings shorter than abdomen	23
20	Compound eyes rounded to weakly conical	21
20'	Compound eyes strongly conical	<i>Oxyopsis</i>
21	Meso/metathoracic femora without lobes	22
21'	Meso/metathoracic femora with small, preapical lobes	<i>Lobocneme</i>
22	Habitus medium to large, body length measures between 62-95 mm. Lower frons pentagonal, spanning approximately as wide as tall, disc with at least 2 vertical carinae	<i>Stagmatoptera</i>
22'	Habitus small to medium, body length measures between 30-55 mm. Lower frons transverse, spanning roughly twice as wide as tall, disc smooth	<i>Parastagmatoptera</i>

- 23 Habitus of moderate size, body measures >30 mm long. Metazona keeled. Forecoxae with contiguous to slightly diverging apical lobes; tibial spur groove placed in distal half near median .
..... 24
- 23' Habitus small, body measures <30 mm long. Metazona smooth. Forecoxae with diverging apical lobes; tibial spur groove placed in proximal half near median *Callimantis*
- 24 Lower frons pentagonal, measures nearly as high as wide, disc with longitudinal carinae. Costal area of male forewings with opaque margin. Stigma transverse, colored bright white in both sexes *Isomantis*
- 24' Lower frons distinctively transverse, measures twice as wide as high, disc without carinae. Costal area of male forewings entirely hyaline. Stigma semi-circular, colored black in both sexes
..... *Stagmomantis*
- 25 Discoidal spines of forefemora arranged in zigzag pattern. Metasternum without auditory organ, earless. Supra-anal plate round *Liturgusa*
- 25' Discoidal spines of forefemora arranged in straight line. Metasternum bearing auditory organ. Supra-anal plate triangular *Gonatista*

Acanthops Audinet-Serville, 1831

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Acanthops parafalcata* Lombardo & Ippolito, 2004

Acanthops parafalcata Lombardo & Ippolito, 2004

Caribbean Distribution: Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Acontista Saussure & Zehntner, 1894

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Acontista multicolor* Saussure, 1870

Acontista multicolor Saussure, 1870

Caribbean Distribution: Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. This species was previously known from the island of Trinidad within its documented Caribbean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded its distribution to an additional island. New records include:

- Tobago – adult male (11.25.2024) observation ID: 253044838; nymph (07.08.2024) observation ID: 228159843

These records represent the first confirmed occurrence of *multicolor* on Tobago and extend the known distribution of the species within the Lesser Antilles.

Angela Audinet-Serville, 1839

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Angela quinquemaculata* (Manuel, 1797)

Angela quinquemaculata (Manuel, 1797)

Caribbean Distribution: Huevos (Trinidad and Tobago), Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. In *Praying Mantises of the Caribbean*, the name *Angela quinquemaculata* (Olivier, 1792) was used following long-standing attribution to Olivier. Anderson (2022: 5) clarified that Olivier did not

author any Mantodea taxa, and that all mantis names appearing in volume 7 of *Histoire Naturelle, Insectes* of the *Encyclopédie Méthodique* should be attributed to Manuel as the true author and 1797 as the accurate date of publication. Accordingly, the correct citation for this species is now *Angela quinque maculata* (Manuel, 1797); this revised authorship is adopted in the present work.

This species was previously known from the islands of Trinidad and Huevos within its documented Caribbean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded its distribution to an additional island. New records include:

- Tobago – adult male (11.01.2024) observation ID: 250093466; adult male (02.06.2024) observation ID: 198622760; adult male (08.06.2023) observation ID: 177111936; adult male (05.06.2024) observation ID: 214115643; adult male (08.30.2025) observation ID: 310389211; adult male (09.13.2025) observation ID: 313753546; adult female (06.12.2025) observation ID: 289080104; adult female (10.08.2025) observation ID: 319691762; adult female (10.21.2025) observation ID: 322353793; nymph (08.02.2024) observation ID: 239387169

These records represent the first confirmed occurrence of *quinque maculata* on Tobago and extend the known distribution of the species within the Lesser Antilles.

Bantiella Giglio-Tos, 1915

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Bantiella trinitatis* Giglio-Tos, 1915

Bantiella trinitatis Giglio-Tos, 1915

Caribbean Distribution: Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. Moulin et al. (2021: 3) reported a single male specimen of *Bantiella trinitatis* collected in Martinique in 1976. Given the absence of subsequent records despite extensive entomological surveys and consistent collecting efforts on the island, this individual is considered an adventive occurrence. As such, *trinitatis* is not regarded as established on Martinique, and its confirmed Caribbean distribution is presently restricted to the islands of Trinidad and Tobago.

Brunneria Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Brunneria orinocensis* Agudelo & Chica, 2002

Brunneria orinocensis Agudelo & Chica, 2002

Caribbean Distribution: Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. An undescribed species of *Brunneria* from the island of Aruba, here informally designated as “*Brunneria* sp. xerophila”, has been tentatively recognized as a distinct taxon based on photographic records submitted independently by multiple citizen scientists. The photographs reveal distinct morphological traits, including unique habitus proportions, foreleg spination, and spinal maculation, which diverge notably from those of other known *Brunneria* species. These characters, together with the geographic isolation of the population, suggest that these photographs represent a new, previously undocumented species. No species of Mantodea has ever been formally recorded from Aruba, making this the first documentation of the order from the island. Aruba’s ecological uniqueness, characterized by its arid, desert-like environment and xeric vegetation, distinguishes it from the nearby mainland of Venezuela, approximately 16-19 miles to the south. The island’s isolation, coupled with its distinct ecological conditions, supports the hypothesis that this species is endemic to Aruba. However, given the proximity to Venezuela’s arid northern coast, which shares some ecological similarities, it remains possible that this species could also occur on the mainland, though no such records exist to date. At present, no voucher specimen has been collected or deposited in a scientific collection, precluding formal

taxonomic description or naming. Therefore, the name “*Brunneria* sp. *xerophila*” is used informally and carries no nomenclatural standing. It is employed here solely to refer to the photographed population and to mark the first verified record of any mantis species from Aruba. Future collection efforts are encouraged to secure specimens and formally resolve the taxonomic status of this remarkable insular lineage.

Callimantis Stål, 1877

Species Checklist:

- *Callimantis antillarum* (Saussure, 1859)
- *Callimantis cubana* (de Zayas, 1974)

Key to *Callimantis*:

- 1 Pronotum slender, metazona measures longer than forecoxae, supracoxal dilation poorly defined, spanning 1.3-1.4 times the width of the metazona. Female macropterous, forewings extending to tergite V-VI *C. antillarum*
- 1' Pronotum robust, metazona measures significantly shorter than forecoxae, supracoxal dilation pronounced, spanning 1.6-1.7 times the width of the metazona. Female brachypterous, forewings extending to tergite III *C. cubana*

Callimantis antillarum (Saussure, 1859)

Caribbean Distribution: Anguilla, Big Ambergris Cay (Turks and Caicos), Caja de Muertos (Puerto Rico), Catalina (Dominican Republic), Culebra (Puerto Rico), Hispaniola, Mona (Puerto Rico), North Caicos (Turks and Caicos), Palomino (Puerto Rico), Providenciales (Turks and Caicos), Puerto Rico, San Salvador (The Bahamas), Saint Croix (US Virgin Islands), Saint Thomas (US Virgin Islands), Tortola (British Virgin Islands), Vieques Island (Puerto Rico)

Remarks. Lombardo & Pérez-Gelabert (2004: 40) documented pronounced morphological and chromatic plasticity in *antillarum* from Hispaniola. Unlike the populations from other islands, females from Hispaniola demonstrate two distinct morphotypes: one with robust/shortened pronotum and significant brachyptery, largely confined to montane habitats in the Cordillera Central and Sierra de Bahoruco, and another with elongate pronotum and macroptery, predominant in lowlands. The elevation-linked distribution, recurrent morphological segregation, and ecological partitioning of the brachypterous morphotype suggests the possibility of incipient speciation. However, intermediary forms occur due to incomplete lineage sorting and continued gene flow between the diverging populations.

Following the 2021 text, Anderson (2022b) documented the occurrence of this species on the island of Anguilla, representing the first confirmed record of any Mantodea species on that island. Since that publication, several new island records have emerged through photographic evidence submitted by citizen scientists to the iNaturalist.org platform. New records include:

- Big Ambergris Cay – adult female (11.23.2025) observation ID: 328617358
- Catalina – adult female (12.15.2021) observation ID: 103414251
- Providenciales – adult male (03.19.2023) observation ID: 151601117; nymph (05.12.2025) observation ID: 281414322
- Saint Croix – adult male (03.30.2025) observation ID: 268094156; adult female (02.01.2025) observation ID: 260392068
- Tortola – adult female (04.15.2025) observation ID: 270624298

These new observations expand the known distribution of *antillarum* significantly and further reinforce the understanding that this is one of the most widespread and prolific mantis species in the Caribbean. As noted in Anderson’s 2022 dispersal note on *antillarum*, the origin point of this species remains uncertain.

Callimantis cubana (de Zayas, 1974)

Caribbean Distribution: Cuba

Remarks. While genitalic and molecular data remain lacking, the Cuban population is thought to represent a distinct evolutionary lineage. Female specimens of *cubana* consistently exhibit a robust pronotum and brachyptery—traits that on Hispaniola are strongly associated with high-elevation morphotypes. However, Cuban habitats where *cubana* has been found are arid coastal forests, not montane or cloud forests like those supporting this morphotype on Hispaniola; thus, their similarity cannot be attributed to convergent ecological adaptation such as altitude-driven wing reduction. Elsewhere in the Caribbean, *antillarum* exhibits remarkable uniformity: all examined populations from Puerto Rico and its satellites (Culebra, Mona, Vieques, Palomino, Caja de Muertos), the Virgin Islands, Anguilla, Turks & Caicos, and The Bahamas show only the elongate pronotum/macropterous phenotype in females. Brachypterous morphotypes are entirely absent, even across islands with widely differing habitat structure, rainfall, and elevation, suggesting that the macropterous phenotype is the dominant and ecologically generalized form across the species' range. If Lombardo & Pérez-Gelabert's (2004) model of unrestricted plasticity applied across the range of *antillarum*, Cuban populations should include mixed morphotypes or show continuous variation linked to local environments. Instead, all Cuban females share the uniform phenotype of robust pronotum and brachyptery across multiple lowland dry forest sites. These findings suggest that Cuba harbors a unique lineage, potentially derived from an ancestral stock that retained or secondarily evolved brachyptery and robust morphology. This divergence could reflect ancient vicariance (e.g., isolation during Pleistocene sea-level fluctuations) or a founder event in which wing-reduction alleles became fixed through drift or selection. The complete absence of macropterous morphotypes in Cuba, despite environmental similarity to islands dominated by such morphotypes, supports restricted gene flow and evolutionary independence.

Epaphrodita Audinet-Serville, 1831

Species Checklist:

- Epaphrodita lobivertex* Lombardo & Perez-Gelabert, 2004
- Epaphrodita musarum* (Palisot de Beauvois, 1805)

Key to *Epaphrodita* Males:

- 1 Lateral lobation of abdominal sternite V absent to slight. Prozonal margins strongly serrate with stout teeth alternating with smaller teeth. Disc of prozona with large tubercles, very rough. Metazonal margins irregularly serrate. Postfrontal sulcus region of head with robust, narrowly rounded postocellar process. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored light brown to light reddish-brown, darkened distally *E. lobivertex*
- 1' Abdominal sternite V with salient lateral lobation. Prozonal margins irregularly crenellate with scalloped outline. Disc of prozona sparsely tuberculate to smooth. Metazonal margins smooth to lightly denticulate. Postfrontal sulcus region of head with low, acutely triangular postocellar process that may be indistinct to absent. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored dark reddish-brown to blackish throughout *E. musarum*

Key to *Epaphrodita* Females:

- 1 Abdominal sternites III-VI laterally produced into salient lateral lobes with irregularly frilled margins *E. lobivertex*
- 1' Abdominal sternites III-IV simple, sternite V laterally produced into large lateral lobes with smooth to frilled margins; sternite VI laterally produced into small triangular lobes ... *E. musarum*

Epaphrodita lobivertex Lombardo & Perez-Gelabert, 2004

Caribbean Distribution: Hispaniola

Remarks. Both *lobivertex* and *musarum* occur within the limestone belt of south-central Hispaniola, spanning parts of Santo Domingo and San Cristóbal provinces. Additionally, nearby sites in the Cordillera Central also harbor populations of both species. Despite this geographic overlap, Lombardo & Pérez-Gelabert (2004: 45) demonstrated that *lobivertex* differs in the structure of its copulatory apparatus from *musarum*. The female allotype of *lobivertex* possesses a more decisive distinction from *musarum*, as its unique abdominal lobation has not been observed in any morphotype of *musarum*. These clear differences in female morphology, coupled with the discovered genitalic divergence in the male holotype, justify species-level separation for *lobivertex* despite geographic and partial ecological overlap.

Epaphrodita musarum (Palisot de Beauvois, 1805)

Caribbean Distribution: Cayo Levantado (Dominican Republic), Hispaniola, Isla Beata (Dominican Republic)

Remarks. Lombardo & Pérez-Gelabert (2004: 46) documented the remarkable morphological variability exhibited by *musarum* in Hispaniola. Their analysis, based on extensive sampling across the island, revealed significant variation in pronotal morphology that, while striking, was not accompanied by differentiation in the male copulatory apparatus, which the authors described as morphologically homogeneous throughout the examined series. Since this study, collected specimens from the same locality have shown to exhibit substantial variation in pronotal length and width, surface sculpturing, wing maculation, coloration of forecoxae, and degree of postocellar process development. These traits are traditionally viewed as diagnostic at the species level in other taxa, yet these variants coexist without evident ecological partitioning in *musarum*. Thus, morphological heterogeneity in this species appears to be structured as discrete or semi-discrete morphotypes, yet without the corresponding reproductive barriers that would warrant taxonomic division. Such patterns parallel those observed in *Callimantis*, where geographic fragmentation and ecological heterogeneity can generate localized selection pressures without fully arresting gene flow. Whether these populations remain cohesive or ultimately resolve into distinct evolutionary units will depend on the interplay between gene flow, ecological partitioning, and isolating mechanisms over extended timescales.

This species was previously known from the islands of Hispaniola and Isla Beata within its documented Caribbean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, a citizen-science observation uploaded to iNaturalist.org has expanded its distribution to an additional island.

- Cayo Levantado – adult male (03.14.2024) observation ID: 202774379

This record represents the first confirmed occurrence of *musarum* on the island and extends the known distribution of this species within the Greater Antilles.

Gonatista Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist:

- *Gonatista bifasciata* (de Haan, 1842)
- *Gonatista borinquensis* Anderson, 2025
- *Gonatista jaiba* Lombardo & Perez-Gelabert, 2004
- *Gonatista major* Caudell, 1912
- *Gonatista phryganoides* (Audinet-Serville, 1839)
- *Gonatista quisqueyana* Anderson, 2025

Key to *Gonatista* Males:

- 1 Foretibiae glabrous. Prosternum pigmented yellowish with contrasting black maculation 2
- 1' Foretibiae densely ciliated. Prosternum pigmented light orange with reddish-brown maculation ...
..... *G. phryganoides*

- 2 Medium habitus. Body length measures 36–47 mm in length; forewings measure 30–41 mm. Pronotum robust, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona <3.6. Coxal lobes unicolorous with anterior surface pigmentation of forecoxae 3
- 2' Large habitus. Body length measures 52–63 mm in length; forewings measure 41–49 mm. Pronotum narrow, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona >3.7. Coxal lobes blackened *G. major*
- 3 Pronotum elongated and narrow; pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation >2.5, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona >3.3. Anterior surface of forecoxae with small, whitish nodules interspersed throughout or with whitish nodules absent. Occurs in Hispaniola, Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands 4
- 3' Pronotum short and robust; pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation <2.3, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona <3.3. Anterior surface of forecoxae with whitish nodule row lined just beneath anteroventral margin. Occurs in The Bahamas, Cuba, Jamaica, and the southeastern United States *G. bifasciata*
- 4 Pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation ≥ 2.6 , pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona ≥ 3.5 . Anterior surface of forecoxae colored orange. Occurs throughout mesic and montane zones of Hispaniola, Puerto Rico or Virgin Islands 5
- 4' Pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation <2.6, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona <3.3. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-brown. Precinctive to Jaragua Peninsula xeric zone of Hispaniola *G. jaiba*
- 5 Metazona length to prozona length ≥ 1.2 . Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black in basal half, anterior half colored dirty yellow. Foreleg trochanters pigmented reddish throughout. Occurs in Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands *G. borinquensis*
- 5' Metazona length to prozona length <1.2. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black, thinly margined on anterior with dirty yellow. Foreleg trochanters pigmented orange, occasionally margined in black around coxal lobes and base of forefemora. Occurs in Hispaniola *G. quisqueyana*

Key to *Gonatista* Females:

- 1 Pronotum elongated and narrow; pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation >2.4, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona >3.1. Occurs in Hispaniola, Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands 2
- 1' Pronotum short and robust; pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation <2.1, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona <2.8. Occurs in The Bahamas, Cuba, Jamaica, and the southeastern United States *G. bifasciata*
- 2 Medium habitus. Body length measures 40–47 mm in length; pronotum length 11–13.5; forewings measure 21–25 mm. Coxal lobes unicolorous 3
- 2' Large habitus. Body length measures 49–53 mm in length; pronotum length 14–16.5; forewings measure 26–32 mm. Coxal lobes blackened *G. major*
- 3 Metazona length to prozona length ≥ 1.3 . Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-purple with salient whitish nodules interspersed throughout. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black in basal half, anterior half colored dirty yellow. Occurs in Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands *G. borinquensis*
- 3' Metazona length to prozona length ≤ 1.2 . Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-brown, smooth. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black, thinly margined on anterior with dirty yellow. Occurs in Hispaniola *G. quisqueyana*

Note: females of *G. jaiba* and *G. phryganoides* are unknown.

Gonatista bifasciata (de Haan, 1842)

Caribbean Distribution: Cuba, Jamaica, Long Island (The Bahamas), New Providence (The Bahamas)

Remarks. In *Praying Mantises of the Caribbean*, the name *Gonatista grisea* (Fabricius, 1793) was applied to the species occurring in the Caribbean and North America. Anderson (2025: 48) re-evaluated the identity of *grisea*, noting the absence of a type specimen and inconsistencies between Fabricius' original description and the diagnostic traits of *Gonatista*. Morphological features and historical context instead suggest that *grisea* likely originated from India and is referable to *Humbertiella* Saussure, 1869. Due to the vague nature of the original description and the impossibility of confidently assigning *grisea* to any known species, the name was rendered *nomen dubium*. Accordingly, *Mantis bifasciata* de Haan, 1842, previously regarded as a junior synonym of *grisea*, was reinstated as the valid name for the Caribbean and North American species formerly referred to as *grisea*.

Gonatista borinquensis Anderson, 2025

Caribbean Distribution. Puerto Rico, Saint John (US Virgin Islands)

Remarks. In Anderson's 2021 text, the name *Gonatista reticulata* (Thunberg, 1815) was used for the *Gonatista* species occurring in Puerto Rico. Anderson (2024: 12) clarified that Thunberg's species is in fact a member of *Tarachodes* Burmeister, 1838 and, as such, the name *reticulata* cannot be applied to the Puerto Rican population of *Gonatista*. To resolve this long-standing misidentification, Anderson (2025: 50) introduced the replacement name *Gonatista borinquensis* for the Puerto Rican species. This corrected name is adopted herein.

Gonatista jaiba Lombardo & Perez-Gelabert, 2004

Caribbean Distribution: Hispaniola

Gonatista major Caudell, 1912

Caribbean Distribution: Hispaniola

Gonatista phryganoides (Audinet-Serville, 1839)

Caribbean Distribution: Hispaniola

Gonatista quisqueyana Anderson, 2025

Caribbean Distribution: Hispaniola

Remarks. In the 2021 text, the Puerto Rican and Hispaniolan populations of "reticulata" were treated as conspecific under the historically misapplied name. Subsequent analysis by Anderson (2025: 55) demonstrated that the two populations exhibit consistent quantitative morphological differences and are geographically and reproductively isolated. As a result, the Hispaniolan population was recognized as a distinct species and formally described under the name *Gonatista borinquensis*. The present work adopts this revised taxonomy.

Isomantis Giglio-Tos, 1917

Species Checklist:

- *Isomantis domingensis* (Palisot de Beauvois, 1805)
- *Isomantis grandis* Roy, 2021

Key to *Isomantis* Males:

- 1 Body length measures 45-60 mm, forecoxae length measures 9-10 mm, forefemora length measures 10-13 mm. Metazona measures 3 times longer than prozona. Occurs in The Bahamas, Cayman Islands, Cuba, Hispaniola, and Jamaica *I. domingensis*

1' Body length measures 70 mm, forecoxae length measures 13 mm, forefemora length measures 16.5 mm. Metazona measures 3.6 times longer than prozona. Precinctive to Puerto Rico
..... *I. grandis*

Note: female of *I. grandis* is unknown.

Isomantis domingensis (Palisot de Beauvois, 1805)

Caribbean Distribution: Andros Island (The Bahamas), Berry Islands (The Bahamas), Cat Island (The Bahamas), Cayo Levantado (Dominican Republic), Cuba, Eleuthera (The Bahamas), Grand Cayman (Cayman Islands), Great Abaco (The Bahamas), Great Exuma (The Bahamas), Hispaniola, Jamaica, Little Cayman (Cayman Islands), New Providence (The Bahamas)

Remarks. Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded the distribution of this species to additional islands. New records include:

- Andros Islands – adult male (05.29.2022) observation ID: 143708270; nymph (04.11.2023) observation ID: 296240568; nymph (09.08.2025) observation ID: 312569500
- Berry Islands – ootheca (03.02.2024) observation ID: 201804628
- Cat Island – adult female (12.12.2011) observation ID: 146431509
- Cayo Levantado – adult male (02.10.2024) observation ID: 204179026
- Eleuthera – nymph (07.07.2025) observation ID: 296123840; ootheca (01.12.2023) observation ID: 146423330
- Great Abaco – adult female (01.18.2024) observation ID: 196964126

The newly documented populations in the Bahamas represent not only the first records of *domingensis* from these islands but also the first known documentation of any Mantodea species from these specific insular landmasses. As in the case of *Callimantis antillarum*, the original distribution of *domingensis* remains uncertain. It is plausible that this species originated in either Hispaniola or Cuba and subsequently radiated outward into the Bahamian Archipelago and Jamaica—or perhaps the reverse occurred, with a Bahamian origin giving rise to populations on the larger islands.

Isomantis grandis Roy, 2021

Caribbean Distribution: Puerto Rico

Remarks. This species was described by Roy in 2021 from a single museum specimen that had been collected by one P. Serre in 1907 from San Juan, Puerto Rico. The solitary male specimen was found in the insect collection at the Museum of Natural History in Paris. After observing that this specimen was significantly larger than typical *domingensis*, Roy prepared its genitalia and noted distinguishing characteristics that were distinct enough to justify a new species. The lack of collection records of *Isomantis* from Puerto Rico over the past century indicate that this species is either extremely rare or possibly extinct. The female remains unknown.

Liguanea Rehn & Hebard, 1938

Species Checklist:

- *Liguanea pediodromia* Rehn & Hebard, 1938

Liguanea pediodromia Rehn & Hebard, 1938

Caribbean Distribution: Jamaica

Liturgusa Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Liturgusa dominica* Svenson, 2014
- *Liturgusa trinidadensis* Svenson, 2014

Key to *Liturgusa* of the Caribbean:

- 1 Juxtaocular processes prominent, rising above dorsal surface of compound eyes. Pronotum robust, stocky. Precinctive to Trinidad *L. trinidadensis*
- 1' Juxtaocular processes level with or lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Pronotum slender, elongated. Precinctive to Dominica and Guadeloupe *L. dominica*

Liturgusa dominica Svenson, 2014

Caribbean Distribution: Dominica, Marie-Galante (Guadeloupe)

Remarks. This species was considered precinctive to Dominica until recent collection records were published by Moulin et al. (2021: 11) that revealed the existence of a sizable population of *dominica* on the nearby Guadeloupean island of Marie-Galante, where this species was noted as being “extremely abundant”.

Liturgusa trinidadensis Svenson, 2014

Caribbean Distribution: Huevos (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Lobocneme Rehn, 1911

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Lobocneme colombiae* Hebard, 1919
- *Lobocneme lobipes* (Redtenbacher, 1892)

Key to *Lobocneme* of the Caribbean:

- 1 Male body length measures 33-35 mm, pronotum 10.5-12, forewings 22.5-24; female body length measures 32-33 mm, pronotum 13.5-14, forewings 20. Distal third of male forecoxae with blackish maculation on anterior surface. Preapical lobes of meso/metathoracic femora slight but distinct. Distributed through northern Colombia and northern Venezuela, extending into Curaçao within the Caribbean *L. colombiae*
- 1' Male body length measures 36-38 mm, pronotum 13-14.5, forewings 28-30; female body length measures 44-45 mm, pronotum 16-16.5, forewings 23-25. Distal fourth of male forecoxae with blackish maculation on anterior surface. Preapical lobes of meso/metathoracic femora salient. Precinctive to Grenada and Saint Vincent and the Grenadines *L. lobipes*

Lobocneme colombiae Hebard, 1919

Caribbean Distribution: Curaçao

Lobocneme lobipes (Redtenbacher, 1892)

Caribbean Distribution: Bequia Island (Saint Vincent and the Grenadines), Grenada, Saint Vincent (Saint Vincent and the Grenadines), Union Island (Saint Vincent and the Grenadines)

Remarks. This species was previously known from the islands of Grenada and Saint Vincent within its documented Caribbean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded its distribution to additional islands within the Grenadines.

- Bequia Island – adult male (08.26.2025) observation ID: 309223033
- Union Island – nymph (06.30.2022) observation ID: 124951505; nymph (06.30.2022) observation ID: 124951388

The Union Island records represent the first confirmed occurrence of *lobipes* on that island and extend the known distribution of this species within the Grenadines, beyond its previously documented presence on Saint Vincent. Similarly, the Bequia Island record not only constitutes a new locality for *lobipes* but also represents the very first documentation of any Mantodea occurring on that island. Alongside a separate observation of *Thesprotiella insularis* (Bonfils, 1967), the Union Island data also rank among the first two confirmed instances of Mantodea recorded from that island.

Mantoida Newman, 1838

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Mantoida* aff. *M. schraderi* Rehn, 1951

Mantoida aff. *M. schraderi* Rehn, 1951

Caribbean Distribution: Huevos (Trinidad and Tobago), Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. This elusive species was previously known from the islands of Trinidad and Huevos within its documented Caribbean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, a citizen-science observation uploaded to iNaturalist.org has expanded its distribution to an additional island.

- Tobago – nymph (07.11.2024) observation ID: 229829243

These records represent the first confirmed occurrence of *Mantoida* on Tobago and extend the known distribution of this species within the Lesser Antilles.

Musonia Stål, 1877

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Musonia remota* Anderson, 2021
- *Musonia surinama* (Saussure, 1869)

Key to *Musonia* of the Caribbean:

- 1 Supracoxal dilation of male pronotum moderately pronounced. Metazona stout in relation to prozona; metazona measures 2.5 times longer than prozona. Prozona lanceolate, margins abruptly narrowing anteriorly. Female supra-anal plate elongate triangular, measures 1.8 times longer than wide. Metazona measures 2.0 times longer than prozona. Oothecae oval in shape, somewhat dorsoventrally compressed, delineation of egg chambers obscured by rough coating of external wall *M. surinama*
- 1' Supracoxal dilation of male pronotum weakly pronounced. Metazona slender in relation to prozona; metazona measures 2.3 times longer than prozona. Prozona elongated, margins gradually narrowing anteriorly. Female supra-anal plate broadly triangular, measures 1.3 times longer than wide. Metazona measures 2.2 times longer than prozona. Oothecae roughly rectangular in shape, laterally compressed, delineation of egg chambers salient *M. remota*

Musonia remota Anderson, 2021

Caribbean Distribution: Hispaniola, Puerto Rico, Saint Martin

Musonia surinama (Saussure, 1869)

Caribbean Distribution: Barbados, Grenada, Saint Lucia, Saint Vincent (Saint Vincent and the Grenadines), Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. Moulin et al. (2021: 4) listed the distribution range of *surinama* as including the island of Antigua. Although the distribution map graphic that is featured in Figure 2 on page 5 of their paper depicts three data points of collection records from Antigua, only one collection data point from the island is referenced by the authors within their text—that of Caudell 1922. In 1918, Professor Dayton Stoner led the Barbados-Antigua Expedition from the University of Iowa, during which he collected a great many “orthopterous and dermapterous insects”. Stoner subsequently submitted these specimens to Caudell for identification and documentation, which was finalized by Caudell in 1922. In that work, Caudell describes five specimens of *Musonia*, stating that they are “all mature and collected on Barbados, the male without further data, one female taken in May and the others on May 14 on Pelican Island.” Given this explicit association with Barbados, it is reasonable to conclude that “Pelican Island” refers to the small landmass formerly located off the west coast of Saint Michael Parish, Barbados, rather than the minuscule private

island in the shallow waters of eastern Antigua, which was not named until decades following Caudell's writing. While *surinama* is indeed known from a series of disjunct island populations across the Lesser Antilles, the inclusion of Antigua within its distribution range, as presented by Moulin et al., appears to have been based on a misreading of Caudell's original locality data.

Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded the confirmed distribution of this species to additional islands. New records include:

- Saint Lucia – adult male (12.30.2021) observation ID: 103973115; adult female (01.04.2022) observation ID: 104356683
- Tobago – adult male (01.13.2022) observation ID: 104865982

In December 2021, naturalist Matt Parr, while conducting a biodiversity survey on the island of Saint Lucia, collected a pair of *surinama* from an overgrown field bordering a cow pasture in the Laborie region. These specimens were later submitted to the author for identification and deposition. This represents the first confirmed record of *surinama* from Saint Lucia, and notably, the first documented occurrence of any Mantodea from the island since Saussure's 1870 reference to *Epaphrodita*. Despite Saint Lucia's biological richness and complex topography, the island remains remarkably under-surveyed in terms of its Mantodea fauna. Given the island's range of microhabitats, from coastal scrub to montane forest, it is highly probable that additional mantis taxa remain undetected.

Oligonyx Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Oligonyx armentariae* Anderson, 2025

Oligonyx armentariae Anderson, 2025

Caribbean Distribution: Hispaniola

Remarks. The species-group name *Oligonyx armentari* Anderson, 2025, originally published in honor of a woman, was incorrectly formed under Article 31.1.2 of the ICZN. Because the honoree is female, the correct Latin genitive ending should be *-ae*, not *-i*. Following Article 32.5.1, which mandates the correction of incorrect Latin formation, the name is here corrected to *Oligonyx armentariae* Anderson, 2025. This spelling is to be regarded as the correct original spelling henceforth.

Oxyopsis Caudell, 1904

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Oxyopsis rubicunda* (Houttuyn in Stoll, 1813)

Oxyopsis rubicunda (Houttuyn in Stoll, 1813)

Caribbean Distribution: Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. In *Praying Mantises of the Caribbean*, authorship of *rubicunda* was incorrectly attributed to Stoll. As clarified by Anderson (2022: 4), Stoll did not formally author any species-group names in his work. The Latin binomial names were instead compiled and assigned by Houttuyn, who created a register based on Stoll's vernacular descriptions. While many names were adopted from earlier authors such as Manuel, several names, such as *rubicunda*, were original contributions by Houttuyn, who alone had access to the most recent species treatments incorporated into the final edition of Stoll's work. The correct authorship is therefore attributed to Houttuyn and is herein adopted.

This species was previously known from the island of Trinidad within its documented Caribbean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded its distribution to an additional island.

- Tobago – adult male (08.22.2025) observation ID: 308338108

This record represents the first confirmed occurrence of *rubicunda* on Tobago and extends the known distribution of the species within the Lesser Antilles.

Paramusonia Rehn, 1904

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Paramusonia cubensis* (Saussure, 1869)
- *Paramusonia media* (Giglio-Tos, 1916)

Key to *Paramusonia* of the Caribbean:

- 1 Prozona very narrow, measuring 3.5 times longer than wide at middle. Metazona rather slender, measures 6.4 times longer than wide at middle *P. cubensis*
- 1' Prozona truncated, measuring 2.8 times longer than wide at middle. Metazona thickened, measures 5.3 times longer than wide at middle *P. media*

Paramusonia cubensis (Saussure, 1869)

Caribbean Distribution: Cuba, Grand Cayman (Cayman Islands), Little Cayman (Cayman Islands)

Remarks. In *Praying Mantises of the Caribbean*, both *cubensis* and *media* were treated under *Thespis* Audinet-Serville, 1831. This classification was subsequently revised in Anderson (2022a: 62), wherein *Oligonicella* Giglio-Tos, 1915 was placed in synonymy under an expanded and redefined concept of *Thespis*, resulting in the recombination of its constituent species. Further analysis supported the recognition of *Paramusonia* as a distinct genus, with *cubensis* designated as its type species. Accordingly, species formerly assigned to *Thespis* in the previous text are now placed under *Paramusonia*.

The confirmed distribution of *cubensis* includes both Cuba and the Cayman Islands. A single historical record from Grand Bahama (The Bahamas) was reported by Rivera & Svenson (2020: 217) from a male specimen collected in 1953. This record remains the only known occurrence of this species in the Bahamian archipelago. Given the absence of additional records from the region before or since this lone specimen, and the considerable distance from its established range, this specimen is here regarded as an adventive individual. Further documentation is required to confirm the presence of an established population in the Bahamas.

Paramusonia media (Giglio-Tos, 1916)

Caribbean Distribution: Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. This species was previously known from the island of Trinidad within its documented Caribbean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded its distribution to an additional island. New records include:

- Tobago – adult male (10.15.2024) observation ID: 247604859; adult male (06.16.2025) observation ID: 290309814

These records represent the first confirmed occurrence of *cubensis* on Tobago and extend the known distribution of the species within the Lesser Antilles.

Paraphotina Giglio-Tos, 1915

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Paraphotina insolita* (Rehn, 1941)

Paraphotina insolita (Rehn, 1941)

Caribbean Distribution: Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. In the 2021 monograph, Anderson (2021: 61) reported a single male specimen of *insolita* collected from Mt. St. Benedict, Trinidad on 04.06.1988 and housed in the University of the West Indies

Zoology Museum. That record was interpreted either as an adventive occurrence from Venezuela, where the species is locally common, or as evidence of a small, cryptic population in Trinidad overlooked due to its rarity. Recently, a citizen-science photograph uploaded to iNaturalist has provided important new evidence: an ootheca from Diego Martin, Trinidad, whose distinctive architecture closely matches that of *Paraphotina*. Although this does not represent a new island record, it constitutes the second and only other confirmed occurrence of *insolita* from Trinidad.

- Trinidad – ootheca (08.17.2025) observation ID: 307155481

The documentation of an ootheca, in particular, suggests local reproduction and strengthens the argument that the species persists on the island at low densities, remaining rarely encountered despite continued entomological efforts.

Parastagmatoptera Saussure, 1871

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Parastagmatoptera unipunctata* (Burmeister, 1838)

Parastagmatoptera unipunctata (Burmeister, 1838)

Caribbean Distribution: Huevos (Trinidad and Tobago), Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. This species was previously known from the islands of Trinidad and Huevos within its documented Caribbean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded its distribution to an additional island. New records include:

- Tobago – adult male (07.02.2022) observation ID: 124491510; adult male (11.29.2022) observation ID: 143320850; adult male (12.25.2024) observation ID: 256228671; adult male (12.22.2024) observation ID: 255949318; adult female (11.09.2025) observation ID: 325883482; ootheca (12.04.2022) observation ID: 143670515

These records represent the first confirmed occurrence of *unipunctata* on Tobago and extend the known distribution of the species within the Lesser Antilles.

Pseudovates Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Pseudovates cingulata* (Drury, 1773)
- *Pseudovates stolli* (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894)

Key to *Pseudovates* of the Caribbean:

- 1 Mesothoracic tibiae lobed. Apices of male hindwings broadly rounded; subgenital plate spoon-shaped. Costal area of female forewings expanding distally then abruptly notched inward to terminate into narrowly rounded apices. Occurs in the Greater Antilles *P. cingulata*
- 1' Mesothoracic tibiae simple. Apices of male hindwings bluntly acute; subgenital plate produced into prolonged triangle. Costal area of female forewings expanding distally then abruptly sloping inward to terminate into acute apical point. Occurs in Trinidad *P. stolli*

Pseudovates cingulata (Drury, 1773)

Caribbean Distribution: Cuba, Hispaniola, Jamaica

Remarks. Historical records of *cingulata* cite occurrences in both Hispaniola and Cuba, suggesting a broader Caribbean distribution for the species. However, no specimens have been confirmed from either island, nor have any photographic observations emerged from these locations in recent decades despite increased survey efforts and the rise of citizen science platforms. This absence of corroborating evidence raises two possibilities: either *cingulata* historically ranged across these islands but has since been extirpated and is now confined to Jamaica, or the early records were based on misidentifications or

erroneous locality data. In either case, these historical accounts warrant careful re-examination through both archival review and renewed fieldwork.

Pseudovates stollii (Saussure & Zehntner, 1894)

Caribbean Distribution: Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Stagmatoptera Burmeister, 1838

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Stagmatoptera cerdai* Rodrigues, 2016
- *Stagmatoptera diana* Rodrigues, 2016
- *Stagmatoptera septentrionalis* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894

Key to *Stagmatoptera* of the Caribbean:

- 1 Blackish maculation on anterior surface of forefemora extending at least to the 8th anteroventral spine. Stigma of male forewing white, oblique, adjacent brownish maculation large, rounded. Discoidal area of male hindwings with yellow tessellation 2
- 1' Blackish maculation on anterior surface of forefemora extending at most to the 6th anteroventral spine. Stigma of male forewing hyaline, linear, adjacent brownish maculation reduced, oblique. Discoidal area of male hindwings hyaline, immaculate *S. septentrionalis*
- 2 Prozonal margins convergent, anteromedial margin narrowly rounded. Blackish maculation on anterior surface of forefemora extending to the 8th anteroventral spine *S. cerdai*
- 2' Prozonal margins subparallel, anteromedial margin broadly rounded. Blackish maculation on anterior surface of forefemora extending to the 10th anteroventral spine *S. diana*

Stagmatoptera cerdai Rodrigues, 2016

Caribbean Distribution: Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago)

Stagmatoptera diana Rodrigues, 2016

Caribbean Distribution: Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Stagmatoptera septentrionalis Saussure & Zehntner, 1894

Caribbean Distribution: Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Stagmomantis Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) thoracica* (Rehn, 1911)

Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) thoracica (Rehn, 1911)

Caribbean Distribution: Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Thesprotia Stål, 1877

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Thesprotia caribea* Rehn & Hebard, 1938
- *Thesprotia filum* (Lichtenstein, 1796)

Key to *Thesprotia* of the Caribbean:

- 1 Metazona length over prozona length 3.2 in females, 2.9 in males; pronotum length over metazona width at middle 11.3 in females, 8.7 in males. Length of mesothoracic legs commensurate to metathoracic legs. Pronotum smooth in both sexes, densely pubescent in male. Supra-anal plate measures distinctly less than three times as long as basal width, supra-anal plate length over basal width 2.4-2.5. Precinctive to Antigua *T. caribea*
- 1' Metazona length over prozona length 3.6 in females, 3.8 in males; pronotum length over metazona width at middle 19.3 in females, 13.5 in males. Length of mesothoracic legs significantly shortened in comparison to metathoracic legs. Pronotum sparsely granulate in both sexes, bare in male. Supra-anal plate measures approximately three times as long as basal width, supra-anal plate length over basal width 2.9-3.0. Occurring in mainland South America and Trinidad *T. filum*

Thesprotia caribea Rehn & Hebard, 1938

Caribbean Distribution: Antigua (Antigua and Barbuda)

Thesprotia filum (Lichtenstein, 1796)

Caribbean Distribution: Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Thesprotiella Giglio-Tos, 1915

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Thesprotiella insularis* (Bonfils, 1967)

Thesprotiella insularis (Bonfils, 1967)

Caribbean Distribution: Basse-Terre (Guadeloupe), Dominica, Grande-Terre (Guadeloupe), Marie-Galante (Guadeloupe), Martinique, Union Island (Saint Vincent and the Grenadines)

Remarks. This species was previously known from Dominica, Guadeloupe and Martinique within its documented Lesser Antillean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded its distribution to two additional islands.

- Grande-Terre Island – adult female (05.24.2020) observation ID: 311127857
- Union Island – adult male (06.26.2022) observation ID: 124923894

The Union Island observation now depicts this species occurring well outside its previously known range, lying considerably farther south of Martinique and with no records from the intervening islands. As with the case of *Lobocneme lobipes* on Union Island, this finding could represent a true range extension, an adventive individual, or evidence of a historically broader range that has since receded. The absence of records from the islands between Martinique and Union may reflect the general lack of focused entomological surveys across much of the Lesser Antilles, particularly the smaller or less populated islands, rather than a genuine absence. It is also possible that the Union Island individual represents a distinct but closely related species. At present, this record is based solely on photographs of a single male, and further research, including specimen collection and morphological or molecular analyses, will be required to confirm its identity and clarify its biogeographic significance.

Tithrone Stål, 1877

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Tithrone roseipennis* (Saussure, 1870)

Tithrone roseipennis (Saussure, 1870)

Caribbean Distribution: Tobago (Trinidad and Tobago), Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. This species was previously known from the island of Trinidad within its documented Caribbean distribution range. Since the 2021 text, citizen-science observations uploaded to iNaturalist.org have expanded its distribution to an additional island. New records include:

- Tobago – adult female (12.04.2022) observation ID: 143670508; adult female (11.08.2025) observation ID: 325938210; adult male (08.05.2025) observation ID: 304129493

These records represent the first confirmed occurrence of *roseipennis* on Tobago and extend the known distribution of the species within the Lesser Antilles.

Vates Burmeister, 1838

Species Checklist of the Caribbean:

- *Vates cayennensis* Anderson, 2023

Vates cayennensis Anderson, 2023

Caribbean Distribution: Trinidad (Trinidad and Tobago)

Remarks. In *Praying Mantises of the Caribbean*, the name *Vates lobata* (Fabricius, 1798) was used in reference to the *Vates* species that occurs in Trinidad. Anderson (2023: 40) noted that this name constitutes a junior primary homonym of *Mantis lobata* Fabricius, 1781, which is a synonym of *Harpagomantis tricolor* (Linné, 1758). As the conditions for reversal of precedence under ICZN Article 23.9 were not met, the junior homonym is permanently invalid under Article 57.2. To resolve this, *Vates cayennensis* Anderson, 2023 was established as a replacement name. The present work adopts this corrected nomenclature.

ADVENTIVE SPECIES

Tenodera sinensis Saussure, 1871

Initial Occurrence Site: Puerto Rico

Remarks. Two iNaturalist.org observations of *sinensis* have been documented from Puerto Rico.

- Puerto Rico – adult male (05.04.2021) observation ID: 77382694; nymph (03.28.2023) observation ID: 154495814

With so few observations and no known collected specimens, it remains unclear whether these observations represent an established population or adventive individuals of *sinensis* into Puerto Rico. The presence of both an adult and a nymph could suggest an intergenerational population on the island, though it is equally possible that these are unrelated introductions occurring at different times. *Tenodera* does not naturally occur anywhere in the Caribbean. However, oothecae of *sinensis* are widely available for purchase online and this species is among the most commonly kept mantis species in captivity (Battiston et al. 2022). Its presence in Puerto Rico could result from purposeful release under the persistent but misguided belief in biological control—despite the fact that mantises, especially large species such as *sinensis*, are indiscriminate predators that consume both pest and beneficial insects, often targeting pollinators encountered on flowers. Alternatively, the individuals may have been accidental escapes from pet enclosures. Another highly plausible route is inadvertent introduction through trade of goods between Puerto Rico and the mainland United States or via human travel in the region. This introduction warrants particular concern, as *sinensis* is a large, highly adaptable predator known to outcompete and displace native mantis species in areas where it becomes established. Its presence in Puerto Rico, even in small numbers, should be carefully monitored to assess potential impacts on the island's native Mantodea fauna and broader insect communities.

LIVE SPECIMEN OBSERVATIONS

01, *Acanthops parafalcata* adult male. Mayaro, Rio Claro, Trinidad 02.13.24 (Photo: J. Touroult)

02, *Acanthops parafalcata* adult female. Tunapuna-Piarco, Trinidad 11.01.24 (Photo: Ian R. Clark)

03, *Acanthops parafalcata* nymph. Arima, Trinidad 11.18.24 (Photo: Ian R. Clark)

04, *Acontista multicolor* adult male. Siparia, Trinidad 02.01.23 (Photo: Anja Williams)

05, *Acontista multicolor* adult male. Scarborough, Tobago 11.25.24 (Photo: Simone Ferreira)

06, *Acontista multicolor* adult female. Port of Spain, Trinidad 11.12.22 (Photo: Hameeda Ali)

07, *Acontista multicolor* adult female. Penal-Debe, Trinidad 03.08.24 (Photo: jacana1969)

08, *Acontista multicolor* nymph. Scarborough, Tobago 07.08.24 (Photo: Amy Deacon)

09, *Angela quinquemaculata* adult male. Scarborough, Tobago 08.30.25 (Photo: Cavan Mejias)

10, *Angela quinquemaculata* adult female. Scarborough, Tobago 06.12.25 (Photo: Cavan Mejias)

11, *Angela quinque maculata* nymph. Petit Valley, Diego Martin, Trinidad 06.28.25 (Photo: Bryan Ramdeen)

12, *Bantiella trinitatis* adult male. Petit Valley, Diego Martin, Trinidad 05.09.23 (Photo: Rashid Ali)

13, *Bantiella trinitatis* adult female. Petit Valley, Diego Martin, Trinidad 07.09.23 (Photo: Bryan Ramdeen)

14, *Bantiella trinitatis* nymph. Tunapuna-Piarco, Trinidad 09.01.24 (Photo: Ian R. Clark)

15, “*Brunneria sp. xerophila*” adult male. Babijn, Aruba 01.15.25 (Photo: Marzaau)

16, “*Brunneria sp. xerophila*” adult male. Oranjestad, Aruba 12.22.21 (Photo: Desislav Iliev)

17, *Callimantis antillarum* adult male. Jardin Botanico Nacional, Santo Domingo, Dominican Republic 02.13.23 (Photo: Francisco Paz)

18, *Callimantis antillarum* adult male. Bonao, Monsenor Nouel, Dominican Republic 04.04.24 (Photo: Juda Isai Martinez Uribe)

19, *Callimantis antillarum* adult female. Jardin Botanico Nacional, Santo Domingo, Dominican Republic
12.26.24 (Photo: Francisco Paz)

20, *Callimantis antillarum* nymph. Jardin Botanico Nacional, Santo Domingo, Dominican Republic
11.20.19 (Photo: Carlos de Soto Molinari)

21, *Callimantis antillarum* ootheca. Altamira, Puerto Plata, Dominican Republic 10.03.19 (Photo: Lisa Johnson)

22, *Callimantis cubana* adult female. Caimanera, Guantanamo, Cuba 02.25.18 (Photo: Wayne Fidler)

23, *Epaphrodita lobivertex* adult male. Los Quemados, Azua, Dominican Republic 07.06.17 (Photo: Francisco Alba Suriel)

24, *Epaphrodita lobivertex* adult female. Oviedo, Pedernales, Dominican Republic 02.18.23 (Photo: Zachary K. Lange)

25, *Epaphrodita musarum* adult male. Miramar, Pedernales, Dominican Republic 08.24.22 (Photo: J. Touroult)

26, *Epaphrodita musarum* adult female. Sierra del Bahoruco, Duverge, Dominican Republic 11.09.18 (Photo: Francisco Alba Suriel)

27, *Epaphrodita musarum* nymph. Cordillera Central, San Cristobal, Dominican Republic 06.21.16
(Photo: Francisco Alba Suriel)

28, *Epaphrodita musarum* nymph. Dominican Republic 09.29.20 (Photo: Juan Taveras)

29, *Gonatista bifasciata* adult male. Ocho Rios, Saint Ann, Jamaica 11.22.25 (Photo: Sheldon Logan)

30, *Gonatista bifasciata* nymph. Cabo Cruz, Granma, Cuba 05.20.25 (Photo: José Alberto Pérez)

31, *Gonatista borinquensis* adult male. Utuado, Utuado, Puerto Rico 01.15.25 (Photo: Sara Puentes)

32, *Gonatista borinquensis* adult female. Barina, Yauco, Puerto Rico 08.03.21 (Photo: Alexander Murray)

33, *Gonatista borinquensis* nymph. Maricao, Puerto Rico 06.20.25 (Photo: Giovanna Andrea Rodriguez)

34, *Gonatista borinquensis* ootheca. Utuado, Puerto Rico 07.05.25 (Photo: Julio Campis)

35, *Gonatista major* adult male. Barreras, Azua, Dominican Republic 08.18.22 (Photo: J. Touroult)

36, *Gonatista major* female. Rio Sanate, Altagracia, Dominican Republic 01.17.19 (Photo: Gustavo Martinez Garcia)

37, *Gonatista major* nymph. Pedernales, Pedernales, Dominican Republic 03.19.21 (Photo: Franklin Z. Howley-Dumit Serulle)

38, *Gonatista major* ootheca/nymphs. Altamira, Puerto Plata, Dominican Republic 08.08.20 (Photo: Lisa Johnson)

39, *Gonatista phryganoides* adult male. Jarabacoa, La Vega, Dominican Republic 10.29.20 (Photo: Carlos de Soto Molinari)

40, *Gonatista quisqueyana* adult male. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 07.30.22 (Photo: Maribel Armenteros de Chotin)

41, *Gonatista quisqueyana* adult female. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 12.21.19 (Photo: Maribel Armenteros de Chotin)

42, *Gonatista quisqueyana* nymph. National Botanical Garden, Dominican Republic 03.29.16 (Photo: Carlos de Soto Molinari)

43, *Gonatista quisqueyana* ootheca. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 12.21.19 (Photo: Maribel Armenteros de Chotin)

44, *Isomantis domingensis* adult male. Santiago de Cuba, Santiago, Santiago de Cuba, Cuba 09.29.25 (Photo: Pedro Mustelier)

45, *Isomantis domingensis* adult female. Playa Aserradero, Samana, Dominican Republic 06.24.24
(Photo: Maribel Armenteros de Chotin)

46, *Isomantis domingensis* adult female. Santiago, Cuba 05.01.88 (Photo: Reinhard Ehrmann)

47, *Isomantis domingensis* adult female. Samana, Samana, Dominican Republic 05.27.24 (Photo: Carlos de Soto Molinari)

48, *Isomantis domingensis* nymph. San Pedro Macoris, Dominican Republic 06.08.18 (Photo: Carlos de Soto Molinari)

49, *Isomantis domingensis* nymph. Ebano Verde Reserve, La Vega, Dominican Republic 08.20.11 (Photo: Carlos de Soto Molinari)

50, *Isomantis domingensis* ootheca. El Cercado, San Juan, Dominican Republic 02.29.24 (Photo: Juda Isai Martinez Uribe)

51, *Liguanea pediodromia* adult male. Mona Heights, Saint Andrew, Jamaica 03.12.25 (Photo: Javian Harriott)

52, *Liguanea pediodromia* adult female. Kingston, Jamaica 10.22.24 (Photo: poyserfelecia)

53, *Liturgusa dominica* adult female. Saint John, Dominica 02.06.25 (Photo: Gavin)

54, *Liturgusa dominica* ootheca. Grand-Bourg, Marie-Galante, Guadeloupe 10.26.24 (Photo: Thibault Ramage)

55, *Liturgusa trinidadensis* adult male. Tunapuna-Piarco, Trinidad 11.16.25 (Photo: Bryan Ramdeen)

56, *Liturgusa trinidadensis* adult female. Diego Martin, Trinidad 03.01.15 (Photo: Mike G. Rutherford)

57, *Liturgusa trinidadensis* nymph. Couva-Tabaquite-Talparo, Trinidad 03.30.24 (Photo: Rainer Deo)

58, *Lobocneme colombiae* ootheca. Christoffel National Park, Curacao 09.16.18 (Photo: Carel de Haseth)

59, *Lobocneme lobipes* adult male. Saint George, Grenada 11.24.17 (Photo: Mike G. Rutherford)

60, *Lobocneme lobipes* nymph. Union Island, Saint Vincent & Grenadines 06.30.22 (Photo: Frank Deschandol)

61, *Mantoida* aff. *M. schraderi* adult male. Tunapuna-Piarco, Trinidad 09.01.24 (Photo: Ian R. Clark)

62, *Mantoida* aff. *M. schraderi* nymph. Argyle Falls, Tobago 07.11.24 (Photo: Amy Deacon)

63, *Musonia remota* adult male. San Pedro de Macoris, San Pedro de Macoris, Dominican Republic 12.22.20 (Photo: Juan Sangiovanni)

64, *Musonia remota* adult female. Puente Higuamo, San Pedro de Macoris, Dominican Republic 11.03.19 (Photo: Franklin Z. Howley-Dumit Serulle)

65, *Musonia remota* adult female. Los Mogotes, San Cristobal, Dominican Republic 06.22.20 (Photo: Franklin Z. Howley-Dumit Serulle)

66, *Musonia remota* nymph. El Cerro, San Cristobal, Dominican Republic 12.28.20 (Photo: Cristian Abiel Miliano Diaz)

67, *Musonia surinama* adult male. Laborie, Saint Lucia 12.30.21 (Photo: Matt Parr)

68, *Musonia surinama* adult female. Saint George, Grenada 07.08.15 (Photo: Kyle Wicomb)

69, *Oligonyx armentariae* adult male. Las Auyamas, Polo, Barahona, Dominican Republic 06.02.24 (Photo: Carlos De Soto Molinari)

70, *Oxyopsis rubicunda* adult male. Scarborough, Tobago 08.22.25 (Photo: Cavan Mejias)

71, *Oxyopsis rubicunda* adult female. Tunapuna-Piarco, Trinidad 11.01.24 (Photo: Ian R. Clark)

72, *Paramusonia cubensis* adult male. Caimanera, Guantanamo, Cuba 02.21.18 (Photo: Wayne Fidler)

73, *Paramusonia cubensis* adult female. Caimanera, Guantanamo, Cuba 06.21.18 (Photo: Wayne Fidler)

74, *Paramusonia media* adult male. Princes Town, Trinidad 12.27.18 (Photo: Questagame)

75, *Paramusonia media* adult female. Princes Town, Trinidad 03.13.21 (Photo: Rainer Deo)

76, *Paramusonia media* adult female. San Juan-Laventille, Trinidad 09.04.19 (Photo: TT)

77, *Paraphotina insolita* ootheca. Diego Martin, Trinidad 08.17.25 (Photo: Dr. Shiva)

78, *Parastagmatoptera unipunctata* adult male. Roxborough, Tobago 11.29.22 (Photo: Amy Deacon)

79, *Parastagmatoptera unipunctata* adult female. Port of Spain, Tunapuna-Piarco, Trinidad 12.12.20 (Photo: Dr. Shiva)

80, *Pseudovates cingulata* adult male. Saint Mary, Jamaica 06.12.16 (Photo: Jack Morley)

81, *Stagmatoptera cerdai* adult male. Tobago 02.17.15 (Photo: Rob Vanderkam)

82, *Stagmatoptera cerdai* adult female. Scarborough, Tobago 12.08.23 (Photo: Cavan Mejias)

83, *Stigmatoptera septentrionalis* adult male. Mayaro-Rio Claro, Trinidad 01.14.19 (Photo: Questagame)

84, *Stigmatoptera septentrionalis* nymph. San Juan-Laventille, Trinidad 05.10.19 (Photo: Lena Dempewolf)

85, *Stagmatoptera septentrionalis* ootheca. San Juan-Laventille, Trinidad 12.20.20 (Photo: Dr. Shiva)

86, *Stagmomantis thoracica* adult male. Sangre Grande, Trinidad 02.07.24 (Photo: J. Touroult)

87, *Stagmomantis thoracica* adult female. Tunapuna-Piarco, Trinidad 11.11.21 (Photo: akashm)

88, *Thesprotia filum* adult female. Penal Debe, Trinidad 07.29.23 (Photo: Bryan Ramdeen)

89, *Thesprotiella insularis* adult male. Union Island, Saint Vincent & Grenadines 06.26.22 (Photo: Frank Deschandol)

90, *Thesprotiella insularis* adult female. Le Lamentin, Martinique 10.19.22 (Photo: Daniel Chantrel-Valat)

91, *Tithrone roseipennis* adult male. Arima, Borough of Arima, Trinidad 04.22.23 (Photo: Amy Deacon)

92, *Tithrone roseipennis* adult female. Tunapuna-Piarco, Trinidad 11.01.24 (Photo: Ian R. Clark)

93, *Vates cayennensis* adult male. Sangre Grande, Trinidad 02.03.24 (Photo: J. Touroult)

94, *Vates cayennensis* adult female. Tunapuna-Piarco, Trinidad 07.08.04 (Photo: Mike G. Rutherford)

95, *Vates cayennensis* nymph. Arima, Borough of Arima, Trinidad 02.08.23 (Photo: cheragoo1)

96, *Tenodera sinensis* adult male. Arecibo, Puerto Rico 05.04.21 (Photo: Victor Raul)

REFERENCES

- ANDERSON, K. (2021): Praying Mantises of the Caribbean. 1st edition. Las Vegas: Kris Anderson.
- ANDERSON, K. (2022): Caspar Stoll's Praying Mantises of the Dutch Colonial Empire. Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 3 (2): 2-98.
- ANDERSON, K. (2022a): Dr. Fothergill's little gray American mantis: Taxonomic Revision of *Thespis* Serville, 1831. Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 3 (1): 48-103.
- ANDERSON, K.. (2022b): *Callimantis antillarum* (Saussure, 1859) in Anguilla. Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 3 (1): 119-125.
- ANDERSON, K. (2023): The Mantodea of Johan Fabricius. Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 4 (1): 27-61.
- ANDERSON, K. (2024): The Mantodea of Carl Peter Thunberg. Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 5 (1): 3-37.
- ANDERSON, K. (2025): Taxonomic Revision of Genus *Gonatista* Saussure, 1869 (Mantodea: Epaphroditidae: Gonatistinae). Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 6 (1): 39-69.
- ANDERSON, K. (2025a): Taxonomic Revision of Genus *Oligonyx* Saussure, 1869 (Mantodea: Thespidae: Thespinae: Thespini). Soothsayer, Journal of Mantodea Research. 6 (1): 3-38.
- BATTISTON, R., DI PIETRO, W. & ANDERSON, K. (2022): The pet mantis market: a first overview on the praying mantis international trade (Insecta, Mantodea). Journal of Orthoptera Research 31 (1): 63–68.
- LOMBARDO, F. & PEREZ-GELABERT, D. E. (2004): The mantids of Hispaniola, with the description of two new species (Mantodea). – Bull. Aragonese Entomological Society (Boln. S.E.A.), (34): 35-48, 3 Tab., 3 Kte., 74 figure; Madrid.
- MOULIN, N., MEURGEY, F. & HUGEL, S. (2021): Mantodea from Eastern Caribbean Islands. – Annales de la Société entomologique de France (N.S.), DOI: 10.1080/00379271.2021.1932590
- RIVERA, J. & SVENSON, G. (2020): The Neotropical “Polymorphic Earless Praying Mantises” Part II: Taxonomic Review of the Genera and Checklist of Species. – Entomological Society of America.
- ROY, R. 2021. Une Nouvelle Espèce du Genre *Isomantis*. – Bulletin de la Societe Entomologique de France. 126 (2): 226-228.